

Trends of aerosol chemical composition from online measurements

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Suspended particulate matter (PM) in the atmosphere is well known to have an impact on climate, environment and human health. Its chemical composition is highly variable in space and time and depends on the relative contribution of sources including natural (e.g., sea salt, mineral dust, biogenic) and anthropogenic (agriculture, combustion, traffic, etc.) emissions; the reactivity in the atmosphere (e.g., gas-to-particle transformations); as well as meteorological conditions and regional or long-range transport. Monitoring the chemical composition of aerosols is therefore essential in order to assess the main sources contributing to ambient concentrations, and to ultimately settle meaningful mitigation policies. Aiming at reducing ambient concentrations, some have been applied in recent years at different scales, including local, national and supra-national scales, although objectives and targeted pollutants varied largely depending on the country and region. Furthermore, in a changing climate, some natural sources, such as wildfires, are observed to increase their emissions in recent years. As a result, the worldwide evaluation of the trends of aerosol chemical composition is of very high relevance.

In-situ chemical composition of non-refractory PM has been enabled since early 2010s by means of aerosol mass spectrometry instruments including Aerosol Mass Spectrometers (AMS) and Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitors (ACSM). Here, datasets from a total of around 20-25 sites across 4 continents, including urban and non-urban sites worldwide, covering the period between 2008 and 2025 with at least 6 years of data, were compiled and (re)analysed. From the non-parametric Mann-Kendall test (Collaud et al., 2020), this analysis will focus on interannual and seasonal temporal trends of aerosol chemical species, highlight differentiated regional and continental patterns responding to emission control policies across different parts of the world, as well as differentiated sources to the ambient aerosol composition. Further, the identification of time series breakpoints and quantile regression trend techniques will be applied to evaluate potential trends in extremes values associated with transient sources (e.g., wildfires).

Reference

Collaud Coen, M., et al.: Multidecadal trend analysis of in situ aerosol radiative properties around the world, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 20, 8867–8908, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-8867-2020>, 2020.